

Reference Energy Measuring System for On-Board Calibration of EMS Installed in Locomotives

Fernando Garnacho¹, Jorge Rovira¹, Abderrahim Khamlichi¹, Pascual Simón¹, Irene Garrido²

¹Fundación para el Fomento de la Innovación Industrial (FFII-LCOE), Eric Kandel 1. Getafe, 28906 Madrid

²Polytechnic University of Madrid (UPM), José Gutiérrez Abascal 2, 28006 Madrid

Tel.: +34 91 562 51 16

E-mail: fgarnacho@ffii.es

Summary: The voltages and currents supplied to locomotives are often subject to distortions with significant harmonic content (odd harmonics, sub-harmonics and inter-harmonics) that comes from train acceleration and braking. The energy measurement is a complex matter due to harmonics content. No reference systems and traceability had been developed before. This research has been developed in the framework of the European project 16ENG04 MyRailS Metrology [1] for smart energy management in electric railway systems.

Keywords: Energy measurement, energy measuring system, calibration set-up, on-board calibration, railway system, harmonic, distorted regime.

1. Introduction

A Reference Energy Measuring System has been designed for laboratory and on-board calibration of on-board Energy Measuring Systems (EMS) installed in locomotives used for AC railways 25 kV/50 Hz, 15 kV/16.7 Hz, with a maximum current of 500 A. This element is a part of the metrological framework for calibration to enable high accuracy energy and power quality (PQ) measurements under highly dynamic electrical conditions approaching the uncertainty limits stated in the EN 50463-2 [2], with a frequency range from a few hertz up to 5 kHz for AC systems. The uncertainty targets for laboratory or on-board calibration calibrations are 0.5 % for AC. Complementary requirements has been stated in the new procedure developed in the EU project [3].

2. Reference Energy Measuring System

The Reference Energy Measuring System is composed by a fluxgate current sensor with an appropriate shunt, a shielded resistive-capacitive voltage divider to avoid interference from external electrical and magnetic fields and two digital sampling multimeters controlled by a PC. Figure 1 shows the schematic connection between sensors, multimeters and PC.

Fig. 1: Schematic layout of the Reference Energy Measuring System.

The current is measured by a sensor based on the fluxgate technology with a ratio error less than 0.1% for frequencies up to 5 kHz. High voltage is measured by a mix resistive-capacitive divider designed by LCOE with flat-frequency response for frequencies up to 5 kHz. The characterization of this sensor reveals an accuracy class 0.2 for a range of frequencies from 20 Hz to 5 kHz.

Figure 2 shows the characterizations carried out to check the performances of the sensors.

(a)

Fig. 2: Frequency response characterization: (a) HV divider; (b) Fluxgate sensor.

The reference system is used to calibrate EMS installed on locomotives using the main voltage and current components with superimposed odd harmonics, sub-harmonics and inter-harmonics given by phase-fired waveform and the burst-fire waveform [2].

A data processing software has been also implemented to achieve a reliable measurement under extremely dynamic conditions ranging in frequencies up to 5 kHz. An ad hoc measuring software has been developed to process in real time the acquired digital data and determine power and energy components. The model functions for active, reactive energy, no active energy and apparent energy based on IEEE 1459-2010 [4], has been used for determining the energy of the reference measuring system for non-sinusoidal waveforms. These formulas have been adapted to digital sampling in measuring time interval corresponding to n periods after the starting time.

A characterization of the developed reference measuring system has been performed in order to achieve the traceability and a calibration to an EMS with its the uncertainty calculations has been performed.

3. Conclusions

The new Reference Energy Measuring System developed in this project will contribute to the improvement of the NMIs metrological capabilities for

the calibration of AC voltage and current transducers and power and energy meters used under harsh electrical conditions, improving their reliability.

The Reference Energy Measuring System has been developed for industrial services. A measuring system working in distorted regimes is needed in trains equipped with an EMF, whose energy measurement accuracy has to be assessed and periodically re-verified, as required by EN 50463-2 [2].

The Reference Energy Measuring System has been designed for laboratory and also for on-board calibrations that means a clear advantage for companies and manufactures which demand this service.

Acknowledgements

The research here described has been developed in the framework of the 16ENG04 MyRailS Project. The latter received funding from the EMPIR program co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. The EMPIR program belongs to EURAMET association.

References

- [1] 16ENG04 MyRailS "Metrology for smart energy management in electric railway systems". EURAMET H2020 Project, EMPIR Program.
- [2] EN 50463-2 "Railway applications - Energy measurement on board trains - Part 2: Energy measuring".
- [3] F. Garnacho, J. Rovira, A. Khamlichi, P. Simón, T. García, D. Istrate, "Calibration set-up for energy measuring systems installed in AC railway systems". IEEE VTS Workshop on Electrical Railway Systems. Gijón, Spain, October 2020.
- [4] IEEE 1459-2010. IEEE Standard definitions for the Measurement of Electric Power Quantities under sinusoidal, nonsinusoidal, balanced or unbalanced conditions.